

The study on development of history curriculum based on authentic learning concepts and history subject concepts for grades 6-11 in schools in Sri Lanka

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Abstract: *This study has attempted to provide practical advice related to the main research question of how to develop an integrated curriculum model of authentic learning concepts and history subject concepts so that the history curriculum related to grades 6-11 in schools in Sri Lanka appropriate the 21st century. This study was conducted under four main objectives that were built cover the research gap identified after a literature review at local and foreign. That is 01. Identify authentic learning concepts and history subject concepts included in the current history curriculum, 02. Exploration of authentic learning concepts and history subject concepts to be included in the new education reform process of 2023 according to the 2015 curriculum framework, 03. Investigating how to develop an integrated learning model of history subject concepts and authentic learning concepts and 04. Redesigning Sri Lankan Grades 6-11 History Curriculum according to an integrated learning model of authentic learning concepts and history subject concepts to appropriate the 21st century. The findings of this study are directly related to improving the potential of the National Institute of Education's history curriculum planning and development process. For this study, qualitative and quantitative methods were adopted in accordance with the mixed methods research paradigm, and data and information were collected using mixed instruments developed according to the study methodology, namely questionnaires, interviews, observations and document review. In the sampling frame of the study, 340 participants were invited in a mixed sample combining probability and non-probability methods, of which 329 actually participated in the study. That sample represents the actual and target population of the study. Its reliability level is 95%. The error margin is 5%. For the analysis of primary and secondary data collected, the results were*

generated according to a mixed analysis procedure combining structural equation modeling and thematic analysis methods according to Microsoft Excel and Word operating systems 2016. The study revealed 10 practical problems in the current 2015 history curriculum. Also, six subject concepts, fifteen subject units, seven subject themes, eight unique learning methods and eleven authentic learning and student creativity development programs were identified to be included in the development of the 6-11 grade history curriculum in Sri Lankan schools to suit the 21st century. Integrating these findings, it is suggested that schools 6-11 history curriculum in Sri Lanka should be developed. The results of this study were compared with the findings of previous research. According to these findings, reviewing the history curriculum planning system and adapting it to modern methods is a very important need of the hour. For that, the top management initiative and involvement of the line ministry is essential. As there are some limitations to such measures, it is recommended to build a study direction for future research on this study. Also, the validity of these study findings should be further confirmed by future research. From the point of view of other stakeholders, i.e. from the organizational and management point of view, attention should also be paid to the relationship between subject concepts that are rapidly changing in time. It is hoped that this research will serve as a strong foundation for future research in considering its implications for researchers, academics, educational management and policy makers on the importance of a system of developing history curriculum to suit the 21st century.

Keywords: History Curriculum; History Subject Concepts; Authentic Learning; Real Life Learning; Future Life Learning; Schools Grades 6-11; Life Beyond School; Integrated Learning Model;

01. Introduction: History is a core subject for grades 6-11 of school education in Sri Lanka. The history curriculum includes the history of Sri Lanka and the global trends that have influenced it. But in development of the curriculum it is a timely requirement to development and redesign using to the history concepts and the concepts of authentic learning. Therefore, the main objective of this study is to develop and redesign the history curriculum for grades 6-11 using authentic learning and history subject concepts

under the proposed new education curriculum Reforms 2023. By (Lombardi, 2014) points out that the Internet and a variety of emerging communication, visualization, and simulation technologies now make it possible to offer students authentic learning experiences ranging from experimentation to real-world problem solving. Andagama, (අරුණම, 2018) states that from 1974 to 2005 the subject of history was implemented as an integrated subject under the name of Social Studies and from 1984 as History and Social Studies. However, due to the failure to achieve the desired objectives in both subjects, the National Education Commission decided in 2005 to include history as a compulsory subject in the 6-11 curriculum, which is still in operation. This study aims to highlight the challenges to the history curriculum of Sri Lanka's public schools and its functional instruction, and to analyse the opportunities for teachers, educators, policy makers and other professionals to overcome those challenges by adopting authentic learning concepts. In this context, it is hoped to identify and suggest solutions to the challenges faced by students, teachers and curriculum developers in implementing the history curriculum so that the new generation of students in the rapidly changing world can reap significant benefits.

1.1 Background information: The study of history is places students according of the educational experience, enabling them to actively participate in their communities and in society, and to be resourceful and confident learners in all aspects and stages of their lives. This research proposal aims to develop an integrated model of authentic learning concepts and history curriculum concepts. Is to explore how it supports new educational trends, how it works effectively, and to what extent the history of school education grades 6-11 is important for curriculum development. Learning-by-doing is generally considered the most effective way to learn. Learning-by-doing is generally considered the most effective way to learn. School Education in Sri Lanka Grades 6-11 History Curriculum Development is done under the Department of Sociology of the National Institute of Education. Parliament of Sri Lanka, (ශ්‍රී ලංකා පාර්ලිමේන්තුව, 1985) accordingly, resource persons including teachers and teachers in service advisors are trained. Also, school textbooks related to the syllabus are prepared by the Department of Educational

Publications. The school curriculum is implemented, directed and supervised by the Ministry of Linear Education and the Provincial Ministries of Education. Also, student development assessment is implemented at the school level and its summative evaluation is implemented at the national level by the Department of Examinations of Sri Lanka. Implementing the school history curriculum today has become a major challenge. Andagama, (අරුඳගම, 2018) it has been pointed out that the focus of the curriculum compilers on the consolidation of the subject of history as an integrated subject is an attempt to quit completely from the public policy of teaching the subject of history as a compulsory subject. It is an attempt to completely to prune the national value given to the subject of history. Dasanayake, (දසනායක, 2021) points out that the success of educational reforms in the past needs to be properly assessed, that a proper study needs to be done on the need for educational reforms, and that non-scientific reforms fail in a very short time. He emphasizes that in carrying out the proposed optimistic reforms, it is essential for the success of the new education reforms to identify the existing situation through proper research and to reach the consensus of the people. Curriculum reforms implemented in 1972, 1998 and 2007, as a whole, brought a number of reforms and changes to the education system, but failed due to lack of stakeholder support at the school level, (Nawastheen, 2019) emphasizes. Studying History Includes all students in the secondary education sector of school education in Sri Lanka and contributes to the provision of opportunities for all, participation of all and equality of outcomes. From study of the School-Based Assessment Program (NIE, 2015) suggests that the evaluation method should be linked to the teaching-learning process of backward children through interesting learning experiences and that the child should be further nurtured without examination centeredness.

1.2 Justification: Allows students to make a greater connection with his future life learning by focusing on the quality of history learning that takes place. In the process of learning history, it is very important to give students interesting and relevant experiences in their lives. This experience is of a high standard. Learning experiences directly contribute to the physical, mental and social well-being of students. The curriculum covers the history of Sri Lanka and global trends and seeks to engage in every

possible way to develop their capabilities and skills in the areas of creativity, innovation and entrepreneurship. (D'Souza & Moore, 2017) Revealed that while the central government maintains standards for national school teachers and academic programs, provincial education policies are regulated in a more decentralized manner, leading to an inconsistent curriculum of variable quality in some provinces. They specifically point out that if further education is not available, questions will arise as to whether students are ready to join the workforce. Beneficiaries of free education have not been able to find jobs that match their educational achievements and the high expectations based on those achievements and as a result have been frustrated and despair led (Jayatilaka, 2012). He further mentions meaningful diversification of education can eliminate the existing mismatch between education and employment and it is a major challenge facing the government in the field of education. History curriculum learning programs that are implemented in parallel with the school education are built on the level of development of the students and actively support their progress at each of those levels. It enables them to develop the learning skills that will assist them in meeting the challenges of life beyond school. It is suggested that priorities be given to studies relevant to the teaching learning process when conducting research on history subject. (NIE.a, 2014) Pointed out that it is appropriate to conduct research on the history subject according to the priorities of the four areas of resource management, subject content deficiencies, evaluation of the supervisory process and updating of the learning teaching process.

1.3 Objectives and research questions

1.3.1 General objectives

- Study of authentic learning concepts and history subject concepts included in the current existing history curriculum.
- Analysis of authentic learning concepts and history subject concepts to be included in the new education reform process 2023 according to the curriculum framework.
- Development of an integrated learning model of history subject concepts and authentic learning concepts.

- Redesigning schools 6-11 grades history curriculum according to the new learning model integrated with authentic learning concepts.

1.3.2 Specific objective: Development of history curriculum for grades 6-11 using authentic learning and history subject concepts.

1.3.3 Research question: How to use an Integrated Learning Model of Authentic Learning Concepts and History Subject Concepts for develop the history curriculum relevant to schools grades 6-11?

02. Literature review:

There has been a great deal of research on curriculum and instruction. However, issues related to the introduction of new education policies and education reforms in line with global trends, and the integration of authentic learning concepts into the curriculum development of school education history with emerging technology remain a challenge for education policy makers as well as educators. (Aydin, Ozfidan, & Carothers, 2017) Points out that there is a lack of significant literature on the challenges faced by educators in implementing school curriculum and how to overcome them. Relevant literature found in Sri Lanka on history curriculum development is insufficient. Therefore, attention was paid to the local literature on different curriculum planning systems and foreign literature such as India, Japan, China, United Kingdom, America, United States and Australia etc. parallel to the study problem. Accordingly, an attempt was made to build the empirical literature and theoretical base related to the research work, to place trust in the research literature related to universities as well as higher education institutions and teacher education institutions. Under that, the concepts of curriculum planning process such as history curriculum, history subject concepts, authentic learning, real life learning, future life learning, life beyond school and integrated learning model were investigated. Accordingly, in this chapter, genuine learning concepts and history subject concepts for grades 6-11 in Sri Lankan schools are balanced and focused on each other and the different planning systems and areas of curriculum development that are used today are compared and the difference is studied.

As (Eilks & Hofstein, 2017) points out, what is curriculum? And considers how it should be derived from the educational vision of the school. It highlights that qualifications form only part of the curriculum. Every school is unique and school leaders must consider how to support implementation, which may require changes to a school's structure and operations. Several basic principles to be considered in the curriculum planning process are introduced. Around the world, the term curriculum is used in different ways. Curriculum has a holistic meaning that includes not only subjects, but also the relationships between subjects, teaching methods and all aspects of schooling that define the learner's experience. This guide uses the following definitions. A school curriculum is a collection of subjects studied in a school year and successive years as students' progress through the education system provided by the school. A subject curriculum is the content and skills included in a syllabus applied through successive stages of student learning. These levels usually refer to school year levels and therefore to a specific age of the learner. Co-curricular activities are valuable educational activities that support learning beyond the school curriculum that the school encourages and supports. The experienced curriculum is the actual learning that students receive as a result of the overall educational experience provided by the school. This includes the influence of the school curriculum, teaching approaches, concurrent curriculum and learning environment. It includes both planned and unplanned or unintended outcomes of the curriculum. The wider learning experience is only part of the process of designing the school curriculum according to subjects and qualifications. A great school's experiential curriculum provides a learning experience that is more than the sum of qualifications, subjects and activities visible in the school timetable. Because careful attention is paid in curriculum design and implementation to learning across and between subjects and activities. All teachers and school staff support the development of the learning attributes and other attributes identified in the school's vision. The school's vision and goals include personal and social outcomes as well as educational outcomes. Learning does not begin or end in classrooms, but rather on the basis of behavioral interactions with the school environment and the wider community.

(Button, 2021) Points out that curriculum scoping and theory provide the basis for curriculum design, development, implementation and evaluation. What should be taught? Who should teach? And what is the content of the curriculum? Who controls it? After finding answers to such questions, curriculum developers can plan the process and move on to the development phase. Conducting a needs assessment is important because it identifies gaps in the curriculum and involves community members and parents. An important step in curriculum development is getting the support of all stakeholders, including teachers. Implementation of the curriculum and its evaluation is the next step in the process. However, (Plate, 2012) points out that due to the lack of systems-oriented educational programs, it is difficult to compare academic findings on current curricula. He further points out that both researchers and practitioners need to devote more time and resources to studying ways of 21st century curriculum development.

2.1 History Curriculum Concepts:

Interpreting "History Curriculum Concepts" involves analyzing the underlying principles and implications of how history is taught and learned within educational settings. But, (Tambyah, 2017) points out that teachers' lack of knowledge about the scope of the curriculum undermines the stated intention of the curriculum to develop concepts of historical understanding. History curriculum concepts represent more than just a syllabus or a list of dates and events. It embodies a philosophy of education that seeks to develop critical thinking, cultural awareness, and appreciation of the complexity of human experience across time. History is not simply a collection of static facts, but must be understood as a dynamic and interpretive endeavor shaped by diverse perspectives, sources of evidence, and disciplinary approaches. But, (Harrell, 2017) research reveals that current middle school social studies curriculum models are poorly designed and do not provide teachers with effective instructional strategies for creating knowledge, developing historical thinking skills, and problem solving. At its core, the interpretation of history curriculum concepts emphasizes the importance of fostering historical literacy. Its primary aim is

to equip students with the skills and tools needed to understand the past with nuance and sophistication. This entails not only acquiring factual knowledge about key historical events and figures but also developing the ability to analyze primary and secondary sources critically, interrogate underlying assumptions, and construct reasoned arguments based on evidence. Also, (Percival, 2018) emphasizes that cross-curricular and thematic forms of curriculum management do not require the exchange of key disciplinary concepts and skills associated with history.

Moreover, history curriculum concepts emphasize the value of historical inquiry as a means of understanding the present and informing the future. By encouraging students to ask questions, explore different viewpoints, and engage in dialogue with the past, educators can help cultivate a sense of historical empathy and ethical responsibility. This involves grappling with the complexities of historical narratives, including their omissions, biases, and contested interpretations, while also recognizing the agency of individuals and communities in shaping historical change. Also according to (Guyver, 2015) Theories associated with conversation, dialogue and discourse show that historiography and pedagogy share some of the same territory. Devices which allow students to get inside an event especially using discussion based on sources followed by presentations or role-plays offer active routes for students of all ages to mirror the processes undertaken by historians. An autonomous model of the teacher of history working in partnership with a world of historians and history teacher educators is preferable to the model of a teacher faithfully ‘delivering’ a national curriculum for political reasons. The use of the Internet for this purpose provides rich opportunities for dialogue between teachers and historians. The interpretation of history curriculum concepts encompasses a broad vision of history education as a transformative and empowering process. It not only equips students with knowledge and skills, but also instills a deeper appreciation for the complexities of the human condition and the role of historical understanding in shaping a more just and equitable society.

(Daniel, 2020) Emphasizes that the concept of history plays a major role in human thought. It is his opinion that it includes the concepts of human agency, change, the role of physical beings in human affairs, the meaning of historical events and that it improves the ability to learn history. Daniel especially points to the ability to better understand who we are in the present by understanding the forces, choices and circumstances that have brought us to our current state. (Llewellyn & Thompson, 2015) Argue that to be successful in the study of history, students need to think about history in new and challenging ways. That is, rather than knowing what happened or memorizing facts from the past, understanding real history is more intense and challenging. Students of history must begin to think and act as historians. They should read widely to find information and evidence and examine historical sources such as documents, pictures, and artifacts. The most important point they point out is that students must be prepared to raise difficult questions about history, to reason critically, to question the validity of historical information, to challenge existing knowledge, and to evaluate the arguments of others. As suggested by the Australian History Subject Concepts and Competencies Framework (Alpha History, 2020) 12 concepts should underpin the history curriculum. That is, the 12 concepts of Continuity and Change, Cause and Effect, Significance, Perspectives, Empathetic Understanding, Comprehension, Understanding, Analyzing, Using Sources, Research, Explanation and Communication are important.

A study was conducted to review the teaching of concepts for a history course and analyse and compare secondary education history curriculum and course books in Turkey in this context over the past decade. The same study (Bal & Bozkurt, 2021) revealed that the concepts to be taught were not clearly defined in the curriculum. The concepts to be taught in the future curricula to be prepared should be clearly mentioned. He is of the opinion that teachers should be guided in this regard. He has suggested that concepts can be taught in history course books using different teaching methods. It says that history course books should include short notes on relevant concepts at the beginning of subjects or in the content. Similarly, he suggests that target concepts should be introduced word for word in the history curriculum and these concepts should be taught in history course books using alternative teaching

methods. (Shao-Wen, 2012) Reveals that the way curriculum is designed is one of the most important factors that predetermine the success and impact of curriculum implementation. Curriculum design and instruction are closely related, and so are curriculum design and outcomes. To achieve satisfactory results, the essence of “curriculum” must be clarified before any curricular endeavours such as curriculum planning, implementation, and evaluation are attempted. He has attempted to illustrate the nature of the term “curriculum” by looking at the literature associated with it. One may find that the relevant literature on the term is exhaustive, and an attempt to illustrate all entries would be an impossible mission.

According to this literature review, a wide range of study gaps in history subject concepts can be identified. That is, the history curriculum can be identified as integrating diverse perspectives, incorporating digital technologies, critical thinking and historical inquiry, as well as addressing controversial and sensitive topics. Integration of Diverse Perspectives; Despite efforts to diversify history curriculum, there remains a gap in effectively integrating diverse perspectives, including those of marginalized groups, indigenous peoples, and underrepresented communities. Incorporation of Digital Technologies; With the rise of digital technologies, there's a need for more research on how to effectively incorporate digital resources, such as online archives, interactive maps, and educational apps, into history curriculum to enhance student engagement and learning outcomes. Globalization and Transnational History; As the world becomes increasingly interconnected, there's a growing need to incorporate global and transnational perspectives into history curriculum, moving beyond a Eurocentric approach to include diverse global histories and interconnected narratives. Critical Thinking and Historical Inquiry; while there's recognition of the importance of fostering critical thinking skills through history education, further research is needed on effective pedagogical strategies for promoting historical inquiry, source analysis, and the evaluation of historical evidence. Addressing Controversial and Sensitive Topics; there's a gap in understanding how to effectively address controversial and sensitive topics in history curriculum, such as colonialism, slavery, genocide, and war, in a way that promotes critical engagement, empathy, and understanding among students.

2.2 History Curriculum Development:

This literature review provides valuable insights into various aspects of history curriculum development. It includes instructional strategies, technology integration, assessment practices, and global perspectives. It emphasizes the importance of evidence-based approaches to curriculum design and implementation in history education. History curriculum development involves the systematic planning, creation, implementation, and evaluation of educational materials, strategies, and experiences aimed at teaching history to learners at various levels of education. This process encompasses the selection of historical content, the design of instructional materials and activities, the consideration of teaching methodologies, and the assessment of student learning outcomes. It seeks to cultivate students' understanding of the past, critical thinking skills, historical empathy, and appreciation for diverse perspectives within the context of historical events and narratives. But, (Plate, 2012) reveals that the existing curriculum has failed to meet the demands presented by today's complex society. Citing John Dewey (1902), he argues that there are two camps of educational thought about the child and the curriculum. That is, the camp of traditionalists who support the traditional core curriculum and the camp of reformers who support changing the curriculum to better reflect the child's interests. Affirming the need to adjust education to meet the needs of an increasingly complex society, Plate further points out that a curriculum must evolve with the society in which it is created. Accordingly, it is clear that system-oriented curricula should be widely used at the primary, secondary and tertiary levels of education.

By studying history, students can develop a better understanding of people and potential abilities of critical judgment. Accordingly, it is emphasized by (Salleh, Mohamad, & Ambotang, 2013) that the individual can be prepared to face the problems of the contemporary world. History is not only a core subject to be learned by students but also a central subject that applies to the school curriculum and to create a balanced harmony for the cognitive, emotional, spiritual, physical and social development of students. They point out that by covering the history curriculum, the new generation will be able to face

the challenges of national development in the 21st century. Emphasizes that lessons and activities should be designed based on the achievement of the objectives of comprehensive global history, and that students' historical thinking can be assessed in various ways as part of ongoing work. Although some underestimate this subject, they also point out that modern technology and multimedia can cover a unique role to meet the challenges and achieve the vision of the education system. What does it mean to meet the needs of modern society in curriculum development? The systems concepts of bi-directional causality and scales shown by the model 2.1 presented by (Plate, 2012) are especially important to understand. It depicts a two-by-two subplot illustrating four different aspects of meeting society's needs. On an individual level, schools must develop in students the skills necessary for employment and to deal with the challenges of everyday life. At the social level, he revealed that this work translates into a number of educational goals, from meeting community or national professional needs to creating a community capable of understanding social needs.

Model 2.1 The co-adaptive relationship between education and society.

	Individual	Social
Society → Education	A. Personal Skills For Everyday Life B. Skills For Employability	A. Ability to understand current social needs B. Ability to meet national occupational needs
Education → Society	A. Ability to forge one's sense of individuality B. Inclination toward personal Development	A. Ability to perceive/respond to future social needs B. Ability to provide innovative means to improve society

Source: (Plate, 2012)

According to (Eilks & Hofstein, 2017) curriculum development is defined as the step-by-step process used by a school to create positive improvements in the courses it offers. As the world continues to evolve, new discoveries must be incorporated into the educational curriculum. It also reveals that innovative teaching techniques and strategies, such as active learning or blended learning, must be

constantly developed to improve the learning experience of students. She further points out that in curriculum planning, three curriculum planning models should be followed as subject-centered, learning-centered and problem-centered. But although there are subject-centered and learning-centered approaches in the existing curriculum, the problem-centered approach is least represented.

However, (Carr, 1998) points out that the curriculum should include the content or subject matter taught in schools as well as teaching methods, learning objectives, classroom organization and assessment procedures. He argues that the curriculum plays an important role in the social and political spheres of a society in inculcating learners into the culture, practices and social relations of their society. But (Paul, 2015) revealed that the curriculum is a contextual social process and that the secondary school curriculum development in the 21st century is completely based on mechanical and static work. (Mohanasundaram, 2018) Points out that school curriculum development should be based on knowledge of the glorious past, rich cultural heritage, value systems, current social needs and future needs of the society. (Alsubaie, 2016) Reveals that for curriculum development to be effective and schools to succeed, teachers must be involved in the development process. An effective curriculum should reflect the philosophy, goals, objectives, learning experiences, instructional resources, and assessments that comprise a specific educational program. It should be a tool that can be used to assist teachers in developing individualized strategies and the methods and materials they need to be successful, as well as a general overview of the subject-specific or expectation. No curriculum will be perfect. But to be effective it must be accepted by teachers and considered educationally valid by parents and the community. Curriculum development should be viewed as a process of meeting student needs and improving student learning. In addition, it cannot be stagnant. The curriculum should be constantly updated. It should adapt to changes in the educational community and society in general. He is of the view that it will then be able to become an effective agent of change in the educational process.

It is clear from the investigation of the above studies that special attention should be paid to Diverse Approaches to Curriculum Design, Integration of Technology, Representation and Inclusivity, Teacher Professional Development in developing the history curriculum. Accordingly, there is limited research on the integration of global perspectives into history curricula, particularly in contexts outside of Western-centric narratives. Therefore, future studies should explore how history curricula reflect the interconnectedness of world history and promote global citizenship education. Also, there is a dearth of research on effective assessment practices for history curricula, including the development of valid and reliable assessment tools to measure students' historical thinking skills and knowledge acquisition. Therefore, it is emphasized that future studies should investigate innovative assessment approaches that align with the goals of history education. In addition, research is needed on the role of community participation and stakeholder collaboration in history curriculum development. This includes engaging students, parents, community members, and historians in the co-construction of curriculum materials and learning experiences that are relevant and meaningful to various stakeholders. Also, most studies in the literature have focused on short-term interventions or isolated curriculum innovations. Therefore, there is a need for longitudinal studies that examine the long-term impact of history curriculum initiatives on students' historical understanding, civic engagement, and identity formation over time. Addressing these identified academic gaps contributes to a more comprehensive understanding of history curriculum development, which may support the continued improvement of history education practices in a variety of educational contexts.

2.3 Authentic Learning Concepts:

Over the past decade, there has been significant scholarly interest in authentic learning concepts, with researchers exploring various aspects of this pedagogical approach. Studies have examined the theoretical underpinnings of authentic learning, drawing from constructivist, socio-cultural, and experiential learning theories. Researchers like (Revington, 2018), (Lombardi, 2014) and (Lam,

2013) have highlighted the importance of authentic tasks, contexts, and assessment in fostering meaningful learning experiences. Studies have found that authentic learning can lead to deeper understanding, higher levels of motivation, and increased transferability of knowledge and skills to real-world contexts.

Authentic learning is an educational approach that emphasizes real-world tasks and experiences to engage students in meaningful, relevant, and challenging learning opportunities. Rooted in constructivist and socio-cultural theories of learning, authentic learning seeks to bridge the gap between classroom instruction and the complexities of the outside world. By situating learning within authentic contexts, students are better equipped to apply their knowledge and skills to solve complex problems, think critically, and engage in authentic disciplinary practices. According to (Revington, 2018) authentic learning is learning about real life. It's a learning style that encourages students to create tangible, useful products to share with the world of people. Not only do teachers bring real-world context into classrooms, but students take real-world problems and issues to solve them and develop solutions that are relevant to the world or community around them. This is learning about the future. Rivington believes that students will become adults in a more complex world and will have to solve real-world problems creatively and collaboratively. There is a growing body of literature on teacher professional development in authentic learning. (Lombardi, 2014) Revealed eight critical factors that must be aligned to ensure a successful learning environment in adopting authentic learning strategies. Namely, 01. Goals, 02. Content, 03. Instructional Designs, 04. Learner Tasks, 05. Instructor Roles, 06. Student Roles, 07. Technical Costs, 08. Assessment have been revealed as the critical factors.

Researchers have investigated how to support teachers in designing and implementing authentic learning experiences (Lam, 2013) as well as the challenges and opportunities teachers face in adopting authentic pedagogies (Sabin, 2021) Authentic learning tasks are grounded in real-world problems, issues, or contexts that hold significance beyond the classroom. By connecting learning to

authentic contexts, students can see the relevance and practical application of their knowledge and skills. (Lam, 2013) Points out that authentic learning is learning that occurs by actually participating and working on real-world problems. It involves engaging learners in real-world complex problem-solving opportunities and thereby training learners' skills and knowledge. He identified eleven characteristics of authentic learning. That is, real world relevance, teacher as facilitator, all Sensations of learners, interdisciplinary, complexity, sustainable tasks, higher order thinking development, collaboration, values, as truly assessable, tangible products. Authentic learning tasks are inherently complex and multifaceted, requiring students to grapple with ambiguity, uncertainty, and multiple perspectives. These challenges mirror the complexities of real-world problems and encourage students to develop critical thinking, problem-solving, and decision-making skills. But, as explained by (Donovan, Bransford, & Pellegrino, 1999) authentic learning is an instructional approach that allows students to explore, discuss, and meaningfully construct concepts and relationships in contexts involving real-world problems and projects. That is, authentic learning empowers students to take ownership of their learning by providing opportunities for autonomy, self-direction, and inquiry. Students are encouraged to explore their interests, ask questions, and pursue projects that align with their passions and goals. Commenting on authentic learning, (Lam, 2013) argues that students learn better in an authentic learning environment. He emphasizes that authentic learning concepts that enhance learning motivation facilitate assimilation of subject concepts, practical integration of studied theories, and prepare students for future careers. (Sabin, 2021) Identified four domains of authentic learning self-directed inquiry, problem solving, learning as an active process, and reflection in real-world contexts. Authentic learning often involves collaboration with peers, experts, or community members to tackle complex problems or projects. By engaging in authentic disciplinary practices, such as scientific inquiry, historical analysis, or artistic expression, students develop a deeper understanding of disciplinary concepts and methods.

Authentic learning emphasizes the importance of reflection and feedback in the learning process. Students are encouraged to reflect on their experiences, articulate their learning, and revise their

thinking based on feedback from peers, teachers, or experts. (Diana, 2019) Presented nine common characteristics of authentic learning. These include real-world relevance of tasks, interdisciplinary learning, student education, open inquiry, exploration and collaboration, community discourse, higher order thinking, mastery of key concepts, flexibility of learning environment and resources. Although authentic learning can vary in its approach, (Rule, 2006) identified four common themes among the various definitions. That is, 01. Presenting real-world problems and findings similar to the work of professionals in authentic learning activities, 02. Projects open to inquiry, development of thinking skills, and meta-cognition, 03. Students engage in discourse as part of learning, and social learning in a community model, 04. Students direct their learning through choice within the scope of the project. The content taught to students in school includes a variety of pedagogical and instructional techniques focused on connecting real-world issues, problems, and solutions. The basic idea is to get students interested in what they are learning, more motivated to learn new concepts and skills, and to reflect what they are learning in real-life contexts. That is, equipping them with practical and useful skills to better prepare them for success in college, professional life, and adulthood, and addressing topics that apply to their lives outside of school is the core principle. As (Lombardi, 2014) points out, authentic learning is learning that occurs by actually participating and working on real-world problems. It engages learners through real-world complex problem-solving and problem-solving opportunities. In this way learners master relevant and real skills and knowledge. In workplace situations and on-the-spot learning, authentic learning activities include role-playing exercises, problem-based activities, case studies and participation in communities of practice. The learning environment for authentic learning is multifaceted in nature. Examples include planning for a specific purpose, making laws, planning a budget, and solving a crisis. The authentic approach to learning is very different from traditional lecture classes. In it, teachers provide students with subject content information that they are expected to memorize and repeat in tests. It promotes understanding through discovery and action in authentic learning.

Thus, it is clear that in the authentic learning process, students collaborate on interdisciplinary projects that provide solutions to real-world problems or challenges, such as designing sustainable solutions to environmental problems or creating multimedia presentations on social justice. That is, students participate in internships, apprenticeships, or community-based projects that allow them to apply their academic knowledge and skills in professional settings, such as conducting scientific research in a lab or volunteering at a local nonprofit organization. Students engage in simulation or role-playing activities that mimic real-world situations, such as mock trials, historical reenactments, or business simulations in a law class. Also, students participate in service learning projects that meet community needs while meeting academic learning objectives, such as organizing food drives, tutoring local students, or conducting oral history interviews with community members. In summary, authentic learning offers a holistic approach to education that prioritizes real-world relevance, complexity, student autonomy, collaboration, and reflection. By engaging students in authentic learning experiences, educators can foster deeper learning, critical thinking skills, and a sense of agency and purpose in their students.

From the above research literature studies, it is clear that despite considerable research on authentic learning concepts, there are several gaps in the literature. It can be pointed out that there is a need for further research on the cultural factors that influence the implementation and effectiveness of authentic learning approaches, especially in different educational contexts. Studies have mainly focused on Western perspectives and have not adequately addressed the needs and preferences of students from different cultural backgrounds. While there is some research on authentic assessment in the context of authentic learning, future research should focus on clear best practices for assessing authentic tasks and experiences. Therefore, future research should explore innovative assessment methods that align with authentic learning principles while providing meaningful feedback to students. Likewise, most studies of authentic learning have been limited to short-term interventions or single-case studies. More longitudinal research is needed that tracks the long-term impact of authentic learning on student learning outcomes,

attitudes, and career trajectories. Furthermore, research on authentic learning has paid limited attention to issues of equity and access. Therefore, studies that examine how to make authentic learning more inclusive and accessible for students from diverse socioeconomic backgrounds, abilities, and educational backgrounds are needed. Addressing these gaps will contribute to a more comprehensive understanding of authentic learning concepts and practices and will greatly assist in the continuous improvement and implementation of authentic teaching in diverse educational contexts.

2.4 Summary: This chapter presented an overview of the research literature related to the 6-11 grades history curriculum. It includes academic methods for developing history curriculum based on authentic learning concepts and history subject concepts for grades 6-11 in Sri Lankan schools. Similarly, the construction of the literature investigation has been done under the four objectives of this study. How can authentic learning concepts and an integrated learning model of history subject concepts be used to develop a history curriculum relevant to grades 6-11? As it is the main research question, the advantages and disadvantages of curriculum planning systems were also discussed here. According to the empirical studies found for the literature review of this study, it appears that there is very little research on the development of history curriculum based on authentic learning concepts and history subject concepts for grades 6-11 in Sri Lankan schools. However, teacher education institutes, colleges and universities in the United Kingdom, the United States of America, Australia, Tanzania, China, Japan, India, and Pakistan have specially confirmed the curriculum planning systems. Therefore, it is particularly important to carry out research on the development of history curriculum based on authentic learning concepts and history subject concepts for grades 6-11 in Sri Lankan schools. Accordingly, according to the primary objective of curriculum planning and development, based on the results of the literature review, the researcher conducted the study according to the mixed method combining qualitative and quantitative methods. Developed semi-structured questionnaire, semi-structured interview guide and observation note guide were used to collect primary data and information, and document review method was used to collect

secondary data. Accordingly, the third chapter discusses the philosophical background, theoretical framework, methodology, data collection methods and analysis methods related to this research.

03. Methodology: This study, conducted with the primary objective of developing a history curriculum for grades 6-11 using authentic learning concepts and history subject concepts, was conducted using a mixed methods research approach. Jayasena and Ambakke, (ජයසේන & ඇම්බැක්කේ, 2015), (Kamble, 2017), (Honorene, 2017), (Khahan, Chairasit, & Pukkeeree, 2017), (Patterson, 2013), (Bainbridge & Lee, 2014), (Peersman, 2014), (Olivier, 2017) and (Odendaal, Atkins, & Lewin, 2016) Discusses mixed methods using mixed strategies research approach, mixed study instruments, mixed methods philosophical background, qualitative and quantitative mixed analysis techniques, theoretical framework, applications, instrument development, and modeling. According to mixed techniques such as document analysis method, semi-structured questionnaire method, interview method and observation method Jayasuriya, (ජයසූරිය, 2017); Abeypala, (අබේපාල, 2014); Galagamage, (ගලගමගේ, 2016); (Chen, 2006); (Creswell & Tashakkori, 2007); (Odendaal, Atkins, & Lewin, 2016) Use of four data collection methods and arguments for developing such instruments are presented. For this study, the qualitative and quantitative methods integrated mixed study methodology are followed according to the mixed method research paradigm. There are three major research approaches quantitative research, qualitative research and mixed method research Jayasena & Ambakke, (ජයසේන සහ ඇම්බැක්කේ, 2015). Accordingly, the mixed-method research methodology, one of the three major research paradigms, is being used for this research study. The fully integrated mixed design methodology is used for this study as shown in Format: 1 comparing the mixed methods are followed comparatively. As (Johnson.b & Onwuegbuzie, 2004) point out, the primary objective of the mixed method paradigm is to attempt to study the problem through the intervention of both other quantitative and qualitative research approaches. (Johnson, Onwuegbuzie, & Turner, 2007) Mixed methods approaches knowledge of theory and practice, including quantitative and qualitative approaches, and multiple perspectives, attitudes, and posture is to try to consider.

3.1 Format: 1 full integrated mixed methods design

Source: (Teddlie & Tashakkori, 2009); (Leech & Onwuegbuzie, 2009); (Creswell & PlanoClark, 2011); (Johnson, 2014) and (Kumarapathi, 2022)

He goes on to describe other study methods used in mixed research methods, such as Questionnaires, interviews, observations, data collection strategies, and research methods, such as experiments and ethnography. Supports a broader understanding of philosophical issues such as Experiments, Ethnography, Ontology, Epistemology, and Axiology. According to (Creswell.a & PlanoClark, 2011) mixed methods are research and related research approaches that combine, integrate and link data, both

quantitative and qualitative, to gain a holistic understanding of the research question. According to Kodithuwakku, (කොට්ඨඵල, 2020); (Zhou, 2019); (CIRT, 2018); (O'Leary, 2017) Quantitative and qualitative approaches are integrated as research components for studies in the mixed methodology. Accordingly, quantitative and qualitative techniques were mixed at various times from the beginning to the end of this research process. Mixed research strategies include quantitative experiments such as surveys, as well as analytical integration of qualitative methods such as target group interviews. Mixed strategies were used in this study in the sense of studying the research problem through different methods and getting a better understanding of the problem rather than following one research method.

3.2 Sampling method and Sample size: This study sample represents all Grade 6-11 teachers, teacher instructors, subject directors and curriculum compilers in the subject of School History of Sri Lanka according to probability and non-probability mixed sampling methods. The total sample is 264 and includes 125 Sri Lankan school history teachers, 120 teacher instructors, 16 subject directors and 03 curriculum compilers.

3.3 Method of data collection and instrument: Data and information were collected using four mixed instruments designed according to the study methods namely questionnaire, interview, observation and document review. As indicated by the Centre for Research and Teaching Innovation at the Grand Canyon University (CIRT, 2018) more than one method of data collection and process were used. Accordingly, in this study a problem solving approach has been adopted for each approach and mixed methods for data collection. Knowledge and understanding based on data and information on the study problem as well as Kodithuwakku, (කොට්ඨඵල, 2014) consist of data sources at each level that collect that data. That is, according to Gunasekara, (ගුණසේකර, 1996) and Pinikahana, (පිනිකහන, 2012) quantitative and qualitative data sources of knowledge based on primary data and knowledge based on secondary data are used for this study. Primary data Abeyapala, (අබේපාල, 2014) is explored using a semi-structured questionnaire, interview schedule and observation protocol according to mixed research

methods. Also, according to Kodituvukku, (කොඩිතුවක්කු.c, 2020) secondary data was collected in a document review method based on books, journal reports, published and unpublished research reports, proceedings as well as various online reports related to the study problem.

3.4 Data analysis: In analyzing the collected primary and secondary data and information, structural equation modeling and thematic analysis methods have been adopted according to Microsoft Excel and Microsoft Word operating systems 2016. That is, the results were generated following mixed methods of analysis combining qualitative and quantitative analysis methods.

3.5 Ethical consideration: Using the Microsoft Office References software according to the APA method, the researcher made sure to properly refer to the original sources of ownership of all types of information and data proposed for the study, and to work responsibly in the study work. (Research & Enterprise Development Centre, 2018), Senadheera & Wanasinghe, (සේනාධීර & වනසිංහ, 2007), Kodituvukku, (කොඩිතුවක්කු.b, 2017) was concerned with copyright, intellectual property, patents and other types of rights. According to Pinikahana, (පිනිකහන, 2012) and Kodituvakku, (කොඩිතුවක්කු.b, 2017) this study was conducted by avoiding the use of fraudulent writing practices such as copying other research reports into his work. In addition to consultants and editors, it also followed research sponsors, publishers, and reviewers, as well as National Institute of Education guidelines, rules, and understanding of the ethical obligations of publishing and disseminating academic findings. Research & Enterprise Development Centre has identified a number of ethical stages in the research process that need to be considered, such as research planning, sampling, data collection and unforeseen needs. That is, the study was conducted according to a set of ethical principles such as autonomy, free and informed consent, accuracy, truthfulness, respect for vulnerable people with special needs, privacy, confidentiality, reliability, fairness, harm minimization and benefit maximization.

Conclusions and suggestions

4.1 Introduction: In this chapter, the findings presented in the previous chapters are discussed with the theoretical support provided by the literature review, research method and process. The main objective is to present the collected data and information according to the study methods and process and to interpret the analysis results, integrate the findings and discuss the conclusions. Possible justifications for the significance and non-significance of the relationship proposed by the study's conceptual framework are also discussed. An overview of the study is presented and key findings are summarized. The collected data and information analysis results of all the studied phenomena are reviewed and the findings are compared with past research.

This study was conducted with the primary objective of investigating the development of history curriculum based on authentic learning concepts and history subject concepts for grades 6-11 in Sri Lankan schools. What authentic learning concepts and history subject concepts are included in the school system's 2015 grade 6-11 history curriculum?, According to the curriculum framework, what are the authentic learning concepts and history subject concepts that should be included in the new education reform process of 2023?, How to develop an integrated learning model of history subject concepts and authentic learning concepts? And how to redesign the 6-11 grade school history curriculum according to the new learning model integrated with authentic learning concepts? According to the main objectives of the thesis, the research findings, results and discoveries are presented critically. Conclusions and recommendations on the empirical validity of the redesigned curriculum model combining prior and modern educational concepts in the implementation of the 6-11th grade history curriculum will be presented.

4.2 2015 Perceptions of the History Curriculum: Related research questions and objectives have been followed by the mixed methods research process in relation to the study findings. As a result, many questions have been raised about the evaluation of both theory and practice, as well as the impact of

developing the history curriculum based on genuine learning concepts and history subject concepts for grades 6-11 in Sri Lankan schools. The following paragraphs present the conclusions of the study findings, combining mixed methods qualitative and quantitative findings mapped to the relevant research questions and the study objectives. Accordingly, the findings of the study are shown to map well with the relevant research questions and objectives.

4.3 2015 Nature of History Curriculum Implementers: Among the teachers and teacher consultants who implement the history curriculum for grades 6-11 in schools in Sri Lanka, male representation is less than female. That is, the gender representation is represented by a ratio of 4:3 women to 4:1 men. 92% of the teachers and teacher advisors who implement the 6-11 history curriculum are over 31 years of age, and 08% are under 31 years of age. There are 84% professionals with professional experience in the teaching service and teacher counseling service according to I, II, III grades. Also, 16% with less than 10 years of service and 84% with more than 10 years of service implement the 6-11 school history curriculum. Also, 16% of teachers with less than 10 years of work experience, and 84% of teachers with more than 10 years of work experience are implementing the 6-11 school history curriculum.

4.4 Education and Vocational Education: This study revealed that among the teachers and teacher advisors currently implementing the 6-11 history curriculum in schools, there are no postgraduates or PhDs. Representation of Post Graduate MA, Med, MSc level is 2%. It reveals that there is a very low representation of higher vocational education. The unskilled people in the field are 30% with 3% unskilled diploma holders and 27% unskilled graduates. Training diploma holders, training graduates and post-graduates are 33%, 35% and 2% respectively. That is, it is concluded that among those implementing the 2015 6-11 history curriculum, 69% are highly professionally qualified.

4.5 Continuing teacher education: History Teachers and teacher counselors have received a significant level of continuing teacher education through in-service sessions organized by the Provincial

Education Offices and Zonal Education Offices. None of them have attended foreign conferences and received further education. Very few people like 1.2% have turned to self-study. 28.8% and 26.9% have participated in the in-service sessions organized by the Provincial Education Offices and Regional Education Offices, 7.3% and 10.9% in the in-service sessions organized by the Ministry of Education and the National Institute of Education. Accordingly, it is concluded that continuous teacher education is not implemented sufficiently according to a specific program to cover all actors of the 6-11th grade history curriculum in Sri Lankan schools.

4.6 21st Century Student Skills Coverage: As a result of the implementation of the 2015 history curriculum, it was revealed that the 21st century student skills that should be developed in school students are not adequately covered. The amount covering those student skills is less than 45% and the amount not covering student skills is more than 55%. Accordingly, this study reveals that there is a clear gap in the 2015 history curriculum. The study gap is 60.16%.

4.7 History subject concepts: Six subject concepts were revealed that should be considered in developing the Grade 6-11 history curriculum in Sri Lankan schools to suit the 21st century. That is, the six subject concepts of source and evidence, time change and continuity, cause and effect, empathy, significance, perspective and competition were identified in this study.

4.8 History Subject Units: 2015 History, grades 6-11 curriculum includes 19 core subject units. Out of which 04 units; That is, it was revealed that the subject units of constitution evolution, past kings, the collapse of civilizations and the early civilizations of the world are not suitable for the 21st century. According to the following 15 subject units, it is concluded that the 6-11 history curriculum should be developed to suit the 21st century. **I. USE OF THE SOURCE, II. Evolution of human development, III. State building, IV. Socioeconomic trends, V. Biography and National Service, VI. Historical Society, VII. Science and Technology, VII. Influence of different cultures, IX. Art and creativity, X. THE**

ADVENT OF THE WESTERN NATIONS, XI. Cultural heritage, XII. Freedom fighters, XIII. Foreign relations, XIV. Global trends and XV. Sri Lanka after independence

4.9 History subject themes: Seven history subject themes have been identified for revising the 6-11 history curriculum to fit the 21st century. That is, the difference between the rates of including and not included in the curriculum of the seven themes of settlement, leadership, lifestyle, ancient science and technology, historical heritage, foreign relations and global trends ranges from $R^2 = 0.0399$ to $R^2 = 0.0329$. Accordingly, it is concluded that the history 6-11 curriculum should be revised to match the 21st century based on these seven subject themes.

4.10 History subject special learning methods: Eight history subject-specific learning strategies have been identified for revising the 6-11 history curriculum to fit the 21st century. That is, there are eight special learning methods namely, activity-based learning methods, module method, authentic learning methods, problem-based learning methods, following KASM method, student-centered learning methods, social and emotional learning and character development and citizenship education. Accordingly, it is concluded that the 6-11 history curriculum should be revised to fit the 21st century by including the eight unique learning methods.

4.11 Authentic learning and student creativity: According to the results of the study, eleven authentic learning and student creativity development programs were identified for the revision of the 6-11 history curriculum to suit the 21st century. That is, I. Constructing history subject content models, II. Establishing a history gallery, III. Forming a History Society, IV. Organization of study tours to historical sites, V. Publication of a subject journal annually/quarterly/half-yearly, VI. Holding history days and exhibitions, VII. Organization of debate/quiz programs, VIII. Conducting research-based studies, IX. Academic papers and newspaper publications related to the subject, X. Organization of thematic electronic media programs, XI. The subject is a unique program of installation of wall newspapers.

Accordingly, it is concluded that the 6-11 history curriculum should be revised to fit the 21st century by including these programs.

4.12 2015 Special Issues in the Implementation of the History Curriculum: Ten curriculum problems faced by teachers in the implementation of the 2015 history curriculum were revealed. That is, I. Inconsistency between the concepts contained in the teacher's guides and the contents of the textbooks, II. Inconsistencies in source information, III. Knowledge-based subject content, IV. Greater emphasis on political content in the curriculum, V. Lesson units are too long, VI. Failure to evaluate practical and creative skills, VII. Relative to other subjects, the physical facilities of the classrooms are less. VIII. Difficulties in procuring additional learning materials, IX. Inability to provide adequate classroom technology tools, X. Inadequacy of internet facilities and tools for online learning. It is concluded that in developing the 6-11 history curriculum to suit the 21st century, these identified problems should be implemented in such a way as to minimize them.

05. Recommendations: This study reveals theoretical knowledge in the field of curriculum planning as well as problems and trends in the implementation of the 6-11th grade history curriculum in order to develop the 6-11th grade history curriculum in Sri Lankan schools to fit the 21st century. Accordingly, some of the identified recommendations to cover the gap in the study revealed by the study conclusions are presented below.

5.1. Among the teachers and teacher advisors implementing the 2015 history curriculum for grades 6-11 in schools in Sri Lanka, male representation is lower than female. Therefore, it is suggested that in the process of human resource development in the field, a ratio-oriented procedure should be followed in order to attract men more than women in order to recruit history teachers. Provisions should be made in the recruitment procedures in this regard.

5.2. There is a very low representation of higher professional education among teachers and teacher advisors who currently implement the 6-11 history curriculum in schools. Therefore, opportunities should

be provided for history teachers to pursue postgraduate degrees such as Ph.D., MPhil, MA, MEd and MSc.

5.3. Activists on the history curriculum in grades 6-11 schools in Sri Lanka do not receive enough continuing teacher education. Therefore, it is proposed to organize and implement in-service sessions at regional and provincial level in a planned manner to enable the participation of all history curriculum actors in schools 6-11 in Sri Lanka. It is expected that the Department of Social Sciences of the National Institute of Education will introduce a functional model of conducting in-service sessions annually.

5.5 The implementation of the 2015 history curriculum confirms that student skills related to the 21st century are not sufficiently developed and there is a significant gap. In order to cover that gap, the history curriculum should be developed so that the 21st century student skills can be adequately acquired. I. Source and Evidence, II. Time variability and continuity, III. Cause and Impact, **IV. sympathy**, V. Significance, VI. Perspective and competitiveness. It is proposed to redesign the 6-11 history curriculum to suit the 21st century according to the six concepts of history.

5.5 The 2015 History 6-11 curriculum comprises nineteen main subject units. It is recommended to remove four of those nineteen subject units and to develop the 6-11 history curriculum to fit the 21st century according to the following fifteen subject units. that is, I. Constitutions broadcasting, II. Past kings, III. The collapse of civilizations and IV. Early civilizations of the world. The four subject units should be removed from the curriculum. As well as, I. Use of sources, II. Evolution of human development, III. State build up, IV. Socioeconomic trends, V. Biography and National Service, VI. Historical Folk Society, VII. Science and Technology, VII. Influence of different cultures, IX. Art and creativity, X. Arrival of the Western Nations, XI. Cultural heritage, XII. Freedom fighters, XIII. Foreign relations, XIV. Global trends and XV. Sri Lanka after independence. It is proposed that the 6-11 history curriculum, based on these fifteen subject units, be developed to suit the 21st century.

5.6 Seven themes of history relevant to the 21st century revealed in this study. That is I. Inhabitation, II. Leadership, III. Lifestyle, IV. Ancient science and technology, V. Historical Heritage, VI. Foreign relations and VII. Global trends. Based on these seven subject themes, it is recommended that the history 6-11 curriculum be developed to be relevant to the 21st century.

5.7 Eight history subject-specific learning strategies were found to be suitable for authentic learning approaches. That is, I. Activity Based Learning Methods, II. Module method, III. Authentic learning methods, IV. Problem based learning methods, V. Adoption of KASM Methodology, VI. Student-centered learning methods, VII. Social and emotional learning and VIII. Character development and citizenship education. It is suggested that the 6-11 history curriculum should be developed to be relevant to the 21st century, incorporating these eight unique learning methods.

5.8 Eleven authentic learning and student creativity development programs fit for the 21st century were uncovered in this study. I. Constructing history subject content models, II. Establishing a museum, III. Forming a History Society, IV. Organization of study tours to historical sites, V. Publication of a subject journal annually/quarterly/half-yearly, VI. Holding history days and exhibitions, VII. Organization of debate/quiz programs, VIII. Implementation of research-based studies, IX. Subject-related academic papers and newspaper publications, X. Organization of thematic electronic media programs, XI. Subject-oriented wall newspaper installation. It is suggested that the 6-11 history curriculum should be developed to fit the 21st century, including these unique programs.

5.9 This study revealed ten unique issues of classroom activities implementing the 2015 history curriculum. That is, I. Inconsistency between the concepts of the Teacher's Guide and the content of the textbook, II. Inconsistencies in source information, III. Knowledge-based subject content, IV. Greater emphasis on political content in the curriculum, V. Lesson units are too long, VI. Failure to evaluate practical and creative skills, VII. Relative to other subjects, the physical facilities of the classrooms are less. VIII. Difficulties in procuring additional learning materials, IX. Inability to provide adequate

classroom technology tools, X. Inadequacy of internet facilities and tools for online learning. It is suggested that the 6-11 history curriculum should be developed to suit the 21st century in such a way as to minimize these problems.

Redesigning the Grades 6-11 History Curriculum for the 21st Century

Table: 5.1 General Key of Findings

General Key on Findings			
	Findings	Quantity	Symbols of General Keys
I	Concepts of history	06	Ch1, Ch2, Ch3, Ch4, Ch5, Ch6
II	History subject content	15	Hsc1, Hsc2, Hsc3..... Chs15
III	History subject themes	07	Hst1, Hst2, Hst3..... Hst7
IV	History special learning methods	08	Hslm1, Hslm2..... Hslm8
V	Student creativity programs	11	Scp1, Scp2, Scp3.....Scp11

Source: Study analysis data

Table: 5.2 Grade - 06 History Curriculum

	Grade	Key findings	Contents of the findings
01	6	I Concepts of history	Ch1, Ch2, Ch3, Ch4, Ch5, Ch6
		II History subject content	Hsc1, Hsc3, Hsc8
		III History subject themes	Hst1, Hst2, Hst3
		IV History special learning methods	Hslm1, Hslm2, Hslm3.....Hslm8
		V Student creativity programs	Scp2, Scp3, Scp4, Scp6, Scp7, Scp11

Source: Study analysis data

Table: 5.3 Grade - 07 History Curriculum

	Grade	Key findings		Contents of the findings
02	7	I	Concepts of history	Ch1, Ch2, Ch3, Ch4, Ch5, Ch6
		II	History subject content	Hsc3, Hsc4, Hsc11
		III	History subject themes	Hst1, Hst2, Hst3, Hst5
		IV	History special learning methods	Hslm1, Hslm2, Hslm3..... Hslm8
		V	Student creativity programs	Sep2, Sep3, Sep4, Sep6, Sep7, Sep11

Source: Study analysis data

Table: 5.4 Grade - 08 History Curriculum

	Grade	Key findings		Contents of the findings
03	8	I	Concepts of history	Ch1, Ch2, Ch3, Ch4, Ch5, Ch6
		II	History subject content	Hsc3, Hsc7, Hsc9, Hsc13, Hsc14
		III	History subject themes	Hst2, Hst4, Hst6, Hst7
		IV	History special learning methods	Hslm1, Hslm2, Hslm3.....Hslm8
		V	Student creativity programs	Sep1, Sep2, Sep3, Sep4, Sep6, Sep7, Sep11

Source: Study analysis data

Table: 5.5 Grade - 09 History Curriculum

	Grade	Key findings		Contents of the findings
04	9	I	Concepts of history	Ch1, Ch2, Ch3, Ch4, Ch5, Ch6
		II	History subject content	Hsc5, Hsc6, Hsc7, Hsc8, Hsc10, Hsc12, Hsc14, Hsc15
		III	History subject themes	Hst2, Hst4, Hst5, Hst7
		IV	History special learning methods	Hslm1, Hslm2, Hslm3..... Hslm8

	V	Student creativity programs	Scp2, Scp3, Scp4, Scp5, Scp6, Scp7, Scp11
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Source: Study analysis data

Table: 5.6 Grade - 10 History Curriculum

	Grade	Key findings		Contents of the findings
05	10	I	Concepts of history	Ch1, Ch2, Ch3, Ch4, Ch5, Ch6
		II	History subject content	Hsc1, Hsc2, Hsc3, Hsc4, Hsc7, Hsc14
		III	History subject themes	Hst1, Hst2, Hst3, Hst4, Hst5
		IV	History special learning methods	Hslm1, Hslm2, Hslm3..... Hslm8
		V	Student creativity programs	Scp1, Scp2, Scp3, Scp4, Scp5, Scp6, Scp7, Scp8, Scp9, Scp10, Scp11

Source: Study analysis data

Table: 5.7 Grade - 11 History Curriculum

	Grade	Key findings		Contents of the findings
06	11	I	Concepts of history	Ch1, Ch2, Ch3, Ch4, Ch5, Ch6
		II	History subject content	Hsc5, Hsc8, Hsc11, Hsc12, Hsc13, Hsc14, Hsc15
		III	History subject themes	Hst1, Hst2, Hst3, Hst5, Hst6, Hst7
		IV	History special learning methods	Hslm1, Hslm2, Hslm3..... Hslm8
		V	Student creativity programs	Scp2, Scp3, Scp4, Scp5, Scp6, Scp7, Scp8, Scp9, Scp10, Scp11

Source: Study analysis data

06. Academic statement: This research includes a review of the literature related to the continuing development of excellence and advanced teacher education intentions in Sri Lankan schools for grades 6-11, based on authentic learning concepts and history curriculum development for the 21st century. To redesign the 6-11 history curriculum, the theoretical and practical practices of teachers, teacher advisors, directors and curriculum developers related to the subject of history in Sri Lankan school education were used. Information and data were collected using the methodological tools of questionnaires, interviews, observations, and document reviews according to the mixed method of qualitative and quantitative methods. After analyzing the content of the collected data and information, the main findings of this study are reported. That is, the nature of those implementing the 2015 history curriculum, the educational level of history teachers and teacher advisors, professional education and continuing teacher education were also given special attention by the researcher. Also, after an in-depth study of 21st century student skills, history subject concepts, history subject units, history subject themes, history subject special learning methods, authentic learning and student creativity, which are covered by the 2015 curriculum, the results were discovered. Furthermore, the revelations in the areas of 2015 history curriculum implementation issues and 6-11 grade history curriculum redesign to fit the 21st century show a unique direction in history curriculum development. The basic meaning of these key findings is that it is an urgent need to adapt the history curriculum from past-oriented traditional methods to future-oriented modern methods. Therefore, to cover the discovered academic gap about the history curriculum planning system, those redesign tables 05.2 to 5.7 have been presented based on the academic findings. Future research is needed to compare study results with prior research findings and to validate the models and procedures proposed by this study.

It is an urgent need to pay special attention to continuing teacher education to ensure the development of Sri Lankan human resources related to the subject of occupational history in the public and private vocational education sector. Therefore, I believe that my research will be helpful for future research literature studies for those who are committed to the excellence of history curriculum efficiency

and effectiveness. These qualitative findings can serve as precedents and guides to each other and/or to full research findings. Conclusions and suggestions on key research findings are based on these study findings. The curriculum was redesigned based on the key areas of the history curriculum system revealed by the study. That field history is essential and important to the modern functioning of the curriculum development system. Implementation and use of the history curriculum design proposed in this study is a very easy task. In doing so, history curriculum planners are able to generate key processes and information necessary for an employable career orientation and act with a practical understanding. From this, there is a positive contribution towards achieving the mission of national education.

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